

Linguocognitive Features of Lexical EnantiosemY

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Abstract. *The article examines the linguocognitive features of lexical enantiosemY using the example of English, Russian and Uzbek languages. The author, analyzing the works of M.Yu. Brodsky and L.R. Makhmutova, considers the classification of lexical enantiosemY, including such types as complete and incomplete, regular and irregular, as well as various types (synchronic, diachronic, internal and interlingual). The article considers examples of lexical enantiosemY, such as the English words dreadful, ever, repose and fame, as well as their analogues in Russian and Uzbek. In addition, attention is paid to phraseological enantiosemY, where examples such as to be death on something and Russian expressions with the preposition "bez" – without demonstrate opposite meanings in context. The study emphasizes the importance of contextual interpretation for understanding enantiosemY in different languages.*

Key words: *synchronic, diachronic, internal, interlingual, complete, incomplete.*

In studying enantiosemY in the English and French languages, M.Y. Brodsky claims that lexical enantiosemY is more characteristic of verbs, which constitute over 50% of all enantiosemous vocabulary in each of the analyzed languages. According to M.Y. Brodsky, lexical type refers to linguistic enantiosemY and is divided into synchronous and diachronic, intralinguistic and interlinguistic categories. The scholar defines lexical enantiosemY as follows: "Lexical enantiosemY refers to the ability of words to combine opposite meanings in their semantic structure: contraries, contradictions, or conversives." Brodsky also distinguishes between complete, incomplete, regular, and irregular lexical enantiosemY. He notes that regular types of meaning in the semantic structure of enantiosemous words are present in every language. In our work, we do not subdivide lexical enantiosemY into many subtypes, but we agree that enantiosemY can be complete or incomplete.

L.R. Makhmutova defines lexical type as follows: "... by lexical enantiosemY we mean a phenomenon in which polar semantic elements are contained within the word itself, i.e., enantiosemY is morpheme-independent. The basic unit of lexical enantiosemY is the enantiolemma." Depending on the type of opposing semantic elements (significative or nominative), L.R. Makhmutova distinguishes between nominative and emotional-evaluative enantiosemY. As the linguist asserts, nominative type is quantitatively limited and can be identified in contexts with minimal volume, while emotional-evaluative is potentially limitless and requires a broader contextual framework. With this classification, the linguist associates lexical enantiosemY with divisions into symmetrical and asymmetrical, complete and incomplete, synchronous and diachronic, usual and occasional, monostylistic and heterostylistic, derivative and non-derivative, as well as typology based on the part of speech of enantiolemmas. According to structural features, L.R. Makhmutova divides lexical type into strictly lexical (non-derivative) and word-formation (derivative) categories.

He is resting in the grave.

Uzbek:

➤ **Тинч ётмоқ** – to rest and refers to the dead.

This word shows polar meanings in the compared languages: to rest and to lie (dead), i.e., living vs. deceased.

Next, let's analyze the word **glory**:

Russian:

➤ **Слава** – wide fame, usually associated with honor, respect, and admiration.

He loved the war for its grand scale, the music of battle, and the loud glory of victory.

No one wanted to earn a bad reputation.

English:

➤ **Fame** – the state of being famous, public estimation, reputation, or renown.

He died at the height of his fame.

Women of ill fame (bad reputation).

Uzbek:

➤ **Машхурлик** – gaining fame, acquiring renown.

The writer's works brought him fame.

Her fame became a hindrance.

The word **glory** carries opposite meanings, depending on the context: honor and fame vs. bad reputation. In translation into English and Russian, it retains its polar semantic properties.

The following words were chosen from a literary text in Uzbek:

Кетмоқ is a polysemous word containing two enantiosemous meanings. In the Uzbek dictionary, it is defined as:

1. to leave one's place;
2. to abandon an occupation or position.

For example, "I left this profession" means "I abandoned it," while "I chose this profession" would indicate the opposite.

The word **o'gir** (heavy) also has polar meanings. It can refer to being calm and composed, but can also mean problematic or difficult character traits.

Finally, we discussed **marosim** in Uzbek, which can refer to both a wedding ceremony and a funeral ceremony. In Russian, "ceremony" refers to a formal ritual or act, and in English, it means a prescribed formal act.

In summary, this article has examined the lexical type of enantiosemymy in the compared languages. The linguistic and cognitive features of enantiosemymy in Uzbek reveal that many words are polysemous, with cases where a single word carries multiple enantiosemic meanings (e.g., *olmoq*, *ketmoq*). In Russian, many words and expressions take on an ironic nuance in lexical and phraseological enantiosemymy, reflecting this semantic feature in speech enantiosemymy. In English, enantiosemymy often manifests through intensification (e.g., "dreadfully handsome"), where negative words are used to intensify a positive meaning.

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